

Findings of the UKSSDC Data Prioritisation Survey

1. Introduction

In April and May 2011 the UK Solar System Data Centre asked users and potential users to complete a brief, online survey. The aim was to find out which data sets and services were priorities for users now and in the future, and to invite suggestions of useful additions. The data centre also asked for general feedback on how satisfied users were with its service.

2. User Profile

2.1 User profile

84.8% of users identified as *research scientists*, 7.6% as *other professional*, 13.0% as *radio amateurs* and 1.1% as *other private interest*.

2.2 Funding Agencies

STFC	53%
UKSA	16%
NERC	13%
EU	6%
ESA	4%
EPSRC	2%
Other funding	6%

2.3 Awareness of Data Centre

70.7% were already aware of the data centre before being asked to take the survey, 23.9% were not and 5.4% weren't sure.

3. UKSSDC Data Holdings

3.1 Online Data Holdings

Comments highlighted the importance of the solar data sets.

Additional data sets that users would like to see: RHESSI, SDO (x2), neutron monitors, Cluster data (or a link to it) (x2), auroral datasets such as all sky cameras, Lancaster riometers, IRIS riometer data, ASK data, Hinode (x3) (EIS data at MSSL), HEOS2 magnetometer data, HESSI, planetary data, Hedin Wind Model, Ulysses, EISCAT, Cutlass, SuperDARN, magnetometers, all datasets that the UK taxpayer has funded in some part.

3.2 Offline Data Holdings

Comments were made in favour of making the data available online for science and accessibility reasons:

"I believe it would be very useful if it was possible to make the data in the physical archive available online. This is obviously not a trivial task, but making these long-term datasets more readily available for analysis would be of great benefit to studies of space weather, where statistics are needed to quantify the risk of extreme events. Long-term change in these datasets may also be relevant to studies of climate change."

4. UKSSDC Services

5. User Feedback

5.1 Use of Related Services

78.9% of respondents also used other data centres.

31 other sites were named by respondents for accessing a wide range of data, only some of which is also held by the UKSSDC.

The Space Weather Prediction Site (SWPC), CDAWeb, WDC for Geomagnetism Kyoto, Space Physics Interactive Data Resource (SPIDR) the Virtual Solar Observatory (VSO) got the most mentions.

5.2 Reasons for using a different service

5.3 User Satisfaction

5.4 Other comments

A couple of respondents stated that they would rather not have to log in, and may use other services to avoid this where available.

Both convenience of sites where more data sets could be accessed together, and simplicity of going to an interface accessing only one instruments data were cited as reasons for preferring another site.

6. Conclusions and Actions

- Respondents suggested many datasets that they would like to see held by the UKSSDC. These mainly fell into two categories: more solar space missions; and STP (solar-terrestrial physics) data from UK groups and projects, especially ground-based instrumentation. Hinode was mentioned by several people and fits the UK funded and solar space mission categories. **Action: Assess possibility of getting new data sets.**
- The majority of respondents were STFC funded research scientists. A small number were NERC funded scientists. This confirms that the data is still relevant and important to STFC science. It suggests that the UKSSDC is still relatively unknown in the NERC community. **Action: Seek better visibility in NERC community. Show STFC that large portion of users are still coming from their community.**
- **Action: Investigate use of links to other data repositories, eg Cluster.**

Results summary written by Sarah James, UKSSDC
25-Apr-2012